

A SIMPLE FLOW RULE FOR CHARACTERIZING NONLINEAR BEHAVIOR OF FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A one-parameter flow rule for orthotropic plasticity was developed to describe nonlinear behavior of fiber composites. Since most fiber composites exhibit insignificant plasticity in the longitudinal direction, a plastic potential containing a single parameter was found adequate. Effective stress and plastic strain increment were introduced to yield a universal nonlinear stress-strain relationship for the orthotropic composite. This plasticity model was evaluated using experimental results of a boron/aluminum and a graphite/epoxy composite.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber composites exhibit physically nonlinear behavior. This nonlinearity is especially pronounced in metal-matrix composites. A number of models have been used to describe the nonlinear stress-strain relationship. Hahn and Tsai [1] employed a complementary elastic energy density function which contained a biquadratic term for in-plane shear stress. As a result, the strain-stress relation is nonlinear in simple longitudinal and transverse extensions. Assuming that fibers are linearly elastic, Sun et al [2] modeled the composite by employing nonlinear matrix layers alternating with effective linearly elastic fibrous layers. This approach is limited by the fact that the nonlinearity was obtained by including third order terms in strains the stress-strain relations.

The physical nonlinearity in fiber composites can also be considered a plastic behavior. Dvorak and Bahei-El-Din [3] used a micromechanical model consisting of elastic filaments of vanishing diameters and an elastic-plastic matrix. The incremental stress-strain relations were described in terms of constituent properties. Recently, Kenaga et al [4] employed an orthotropic elastic-plastic formulation to characterize the nonlinear behavior of a boron/aluminum composite. This

orthotropic plasticity model contained three parameters which were determined experimentally.

The present study furthers the theory developed in [4] by incorporating the fact that for most unidirectional fiber composites the stress-strain relation in the fiber direction is basically linearly elastic. The plastic behavior of composites is then characterized by a single parameter.

A SINGLE PARAMETER PLASTICITY MODEL

A yield function that is quadratic in stresses is assumed for the general 3-D fiber composite as

$$\begin{aligned}
 2f(\sigma_{ij}) &= a_{11}\sigma_{11}^2 + a_{22}\sigma_{22}^2 + a_{33}\sigma_{33}^2 \\
 &+ 2a_{12}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 2a_{13}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33} + 2a_{23}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} \\
 &+ 2a_{44}\sigma_{23}^2 + 2a_{55}\sigma_{13}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2 \\
 &= k
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where the stresses σ_{ij} refer to the principal material directions, and k is a state variable. The coefficients a_{ij} describe the amount of anisotropy in the plasticity. This expression satisfies the orthotropy condition. The values of a_{ij} can be determined from the experimental data. This function reduces to von Mises yield criterion for isotropic solids when the a_{ij} have the values

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{11} &= a_{22} = a_{33} = 2/3 \\
 a_{12} &= a_{13} = a_{23} = -1/3 \\
 a_{44} &= a_{55} = a_{66} = 1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The Hill-type yield function for orthotropic materials [5] is a special case of Eq. (1). In general, the yield function given by Eq. (1) implies neither the incompressibility of plastic strains nor the assumption that hydrostatic stresses result in no plastic deformation.

By using the associated flow rule, the incremental plastic strains can be written in terms of the plastic potential f as

$$d\epsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\lambda \tag{3}$$

where the superscript p denotes plasticity, and $d\lambda$ is a proportionality factor.

The increment of plastic work per unit volume is given by

$$dW^p = \sigma_{ij}d\epsilon_{ij}^p = 2fd\lambda \tag{4}$$

Let the effective stress $\bar{\sigma}$ be defined as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{3f} \quad (5)$$

The effective plastic strain increment $d\bar{\epsilon}^P$ can be defined such that

$$dW^P = \bar{\sigma}d\bar{\epsilon}^P \quad (6)$$

Substitution of Eqs. (4) and (5) into (6) yields

$$d\bar{\epsilon}^P = \frac{2}{3} \bar{\sigma}d\lambda \quad (7)$$

and

$$d\lambda = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{\epsilon}^P}{d\bar{\sigma}} \right) \left(\frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{\bar{\sigma}} \right) \quad (8)$$

Comparing Eqs. (1) and (5), we find that

$$k = \frac{2}{3} \bar{\sigma}^2 \quad (9)$$

Since the incremental strain $d\epsilon_{ij}$ is assumed to be small, we are able to linearly decompose it into the elastic part $d\epsilon_{ij}^e$ and the plastic part $d\epsilon_{ij}^p$ as

$$d\epsilon_{ij} = d\epsilon_{ij}^e + d\epsilon_{ij}^p \quad (10)$$

Consider a state of plane stress parallel to the $x_1 - x_2$ plane. The plastic potential function reduces to

$$2f = a_{11}\sigma_{11}^2 + a_{22}\sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{12}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 2a_{22}\sigma_{12}^2 \quad (11)$$

Without loss of generality, we further set $a_{22} = 1$.

Much experimental data show that fiber composites behave linearly when loaded in the fiber direction. Thus, we assume that

$$d\epsilon_{11}^p = 0 \quad (12)$$

which leads to the condition

$$a_{11} = a_{12} = 0 \quad (13)$$

As a result, we obtain a one-parameter plastic potential

$$2f = \sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2 \quad (14)$$

From this plastic potential, the plastic strain increments are derived:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} d\epsilon_{11}^p \\ d\epsilon_{22}^p \\ d\gamma_{12}^p \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \sigma_{22} \\ 2a_{66}\sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} d\lambda \quad (15)$$

where $\gamma_{12} = 2\epsilon_{12}$ is an engineering shear strain. The corresponding effective stress is given by

$$\bar{\sigma} = \left[\frac{3}{2}(\sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (16)$$

and the effective plastic strain increment is obtained from Eq. (7) as

$$d\bar{\epsilon}^p = \left[\frac{2}{3}(\sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} d\lambda \quad (17)$$

The complete description of the plastic incremental strain-stress relations now depend on the value of a_{66} and the $\bar{\epsilon}^p - \bar{\sigma}$ relation.

OFF-AXIS TENSION TEST

The material constant a_{66} and the $\bar{\epsilon}^p - \bar{\sigma}$ relation were determined from static tension tests on off-axis coupon specimens.

Let x-axis be the uniaxial loading direction which makes an angle θ with the fiber direction x_1 -axis. The stresses referring to the material principal axes are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{11} &= \cos^2\theta \sigma_x \\ \sigma_{22} &= \sin^2\theta \sigma_x \\ \sigma_{12} &= -\sin\theta\cos\theta \sigma_x \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where σ_x is the applied stress.

Substitution of Eq. (18) into Eqs. (16) and (17) yields

$$\bar{\sigma} = h(\theta) \sigma_x \quad (19)$$

and

$$d\bar{\epsilon}^p = \frac{2}{3} h(\theta) \sigma_x d\lambda \quad (20)$$

respectively. In Eqs. (19-20)

$$h(\theta) = \left[\frac{3}{2} (\sin^4 \theta + 2a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (21)$$

From the coordinate transformation law, we have

$$d\epsilon_x^P = \cos^2 \theta d\epsilon_{11}^P + \sin^2 \theta d\epsilon_{22}^P - \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta d\sigma_{12}^P \quad (22)$$

where $d\epsilon_x^P$ is the plastic strain increment measured in x-direction. Using Eqs. (15) and (18), we obtain from Eq. (22) the following

$$d\epsilon_x^P = [\sin^4 \theta + 2a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta] \sigma_x d\lambda = \frac{2}{3} h^2(\theta) \sigma_x d\lambda \quad (23)$$

Comparison of Eqs. (20) and (23) leads to

$$d\bar{\epsilon}^P = d\epsilon_x^P / h(\theta) \quad (24)$$

Integration of Eq. (24) yields

$$\bar{\epsilon}^P = \epsilon_x^P / h(\theta) \quad (25)$$

Using the relations given by Eqs. (19) and (25), the relation between $\bar{\epsilon}^P$ and $\bar{\sigma}$ can be established from the $\sigma_x - \epsilon_x^P$ relation which can be experimentally obtained from the off-axis tension test. In fact, we have

$$\frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{d\bar{\epsilon}^P} = h^2(\theta) \frac{d\sigma_x}{d\epsilon_x^P} \quad (26)$$

and

$$d\lambda = \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{h^2(\theta)} \frac{d\epsilon_x^P}{d\sigma_x} \frac{d\sigma_x}{\sigma_x} \quad (27)$$

Using Eqs. (19) and (25), the measured σ_x and ϵ_x^P are plotted in terms of $\bar{\sigma}$ versus $\bar{\epsilon}^P$. For different values of θ , the resulting $\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\epsilon}^P$ curves must be identical. This is achieved by selecting a proper value for a_{66} .

Experimental results indicate that for fiber composites there is no well defined yield point. In fact, nonlinearity appears in the stress-strain relation gradually. In view of this, a power law is used:

$$\bar{\epsilon}^P = A \bar{\sigma}^n \quad (28)$$

Such a model allows initial yielding at the moment the stress is applied. Because of the power law, however, the amount of plastic strain is very small for low levels

of applied stress.

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The foregoing one-parameter plasticity model was employed to describe non-linear behavior of boron/aluminum and graphite/epoxy composites. For boron/aluminum, the off-axis tension test data were obtained from the report by Sun et al [6]. The off-axis stress-strain curves of the AS/3501-5 graphite/epoxy composite used in this study were published in [7].

For boron/aluminum, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} a_{66} &= 2.0 \\ \bar{\epsilon}^P &= 0.3 \times 10^{-10} \bar{\sigma}^{5.8} \quad (\bar{\sigma} \text{ in ksi}) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

For graphite/epoxy, the result is

$$\begin{aligned} a_{66} &= 1.25 \\ \bar{\epsilon}^P &= 0.9 \times 10^{-7} \bar{\sigma}^{3.7} \quad (\bar{\sigma} \text{ in ksi}) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Figures 1 and 2 show the effective stress-plastic strain ($\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\epsilon}^P$) relations for both composite materials. The experimentally measured data obtained for different θ values are plotted using the respective a_{66} values for the two composites. It is evident that the plastic stress-strain curves collapse into one in terms of effective stress and effective plastic strain. Further, one parameter (a_{66}) appears to be sufficient to characterize the orthotropic property.

Figure 3 shows the total stress-strain relation for uniaxial tension of off-axis boron/aluminum specimens. The total longitudinal strain in the loading direction is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} + \epsilon_x^P \\ &= \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} + [h(\theta)]^{n+1} A \sigma_x^n \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where E_x is the apparent modulus of elasticity of the off-axis specimen which can be obtained from the stress-strain curve for the off-axis specimen or from the transformation equation

$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{1}{E_1} \cos^4 \theta + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \right) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{1}{E_2} \sin^4 \theta \quad (32)$$

In Eq. (32), E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} are the orthotropic elastic constants for the fiber composite.

Figure 1. Stress-plastic strain relations plotted in terms of effective stress and effective plastic strain for boron/aluminum composite loaded from the one-parameter ($a_{66} = 2.0$) plastic potential.

Figure 2. Effective stress-effective plastic strain relation for graphite/epoxy composite. Solid line is predicted with $a_{66} = 1.25$.

For the graphite/epoxy off-axis specimens, the measured and predicted stress-strain curves for a number of θ 's are shown in Figs. 4-5.

From the comparisons presented in Figs. 3-5, it is concluded that the present formulation using the $\bar{\epsilon}^P - \bar{\sigma}$ relation and a one-parameter plastic potential is capable of describing the nonlinear stress-strain behavior of fiber composites under a state of combined stress relative to the material principal directions.

Figure 3. Comparison of off-axis stress-strain curves for boron/aluminum obtained from experiment and the one-parameter plasticity model.

Figure 4. Comparison of measured and predicted off-axis stress-strain curves for graphite/epoxy composites loaded at $\theta = 6^\circ, 12^\circ, 20^\circ$.

Figure 5. Comparison of measured and predicted off-axis stress-strain curves for graphite/epoxy composites loaded at $\theta = 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 80^\circ$.

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